

Overall quality assessment of SKOS thesauri: an AHP-based approach

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Abstract

The exploitation of Linked Data technology allows creating a federation of interconnected thesauri, namely Thesaurus Framework (TF), aiming at providing shared standards and scientific terms for a common understanding of data among communities operating in different fields. The paper proposes a methodology for the Thesauri Quality Assessment (TQA), defined as the process aimed at supporting the decision maker in thesauri selection based on the exploitation of an overall quality measure. This measure takes into account the subjective perceptions of the decision maker according with the reuse of thesauri in a specific application context. The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) methodology is adopted to capture both subjective and objective facets involved in the TQA thus to provide a ranking of the assessed thesauri. The application of the methodology to a real set of thesauri, encoded according to the Simple Knowledge Organization Systems (SKOS) standard, is illustrated considering two distinct application contexts and a step-by-step explanation of how the approach supports the decision tasks involved in the creation and the management of a TF is provided.

Keywords

Thesauri Quality Assessment; overall quality measure; linked data; Multiple Attribute Decision Methods; Analytic Hierarchy Process

1. Introduction

Terminological resources such as thesauri, more structured kind of controlled vocabularies [1], are instances of Knowledge Organization Systems (KOS) usually employed within information retrieval systems in order to provide a uniform description for the information resources as well as in the search and discovery process [2].

Thesauri are widely employed as common ground enabling users to share and agree upon scientific/technical terms and to express them in multiple languages. Several thesauri have been deployed by domain-specific communities embodying various points of view based on alternative conceptualizations. Their development reflects different scopes and implies quite a range of levels of abstraction and detail. In particular last years have witnessed the growing interest of many organizations and projects activities [3-5] in publishing their terminological resources on the web according to the Linked Data (LD) initiative namely the Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS) [6]. SKOS has been designed to supply a common data model for KOS and KOS expressed in SKOS can be published according to the LD principles [7]. The main concept of LD stems from the idea of using the web to connect data and aims at transforming the web into a global knowledge base [8]. The exploitation of LD technologies allows making thesauri available not just as isolated data islands but as part of an interconnected federation of thesauri, referred to as TF, able to supply wider extensive terminology for different communities working on the same domain [9, 10].

The activity of identification and selection of reusable thesauri is a critical task. Some recent works address the vocabularies reusability from several points of view (e.g. domain coverage, multilingual support, technological aspects)

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[11, 12]. Nevertheless, of paramount importance for vocabularies reuse is the quality issue, which is strongly affected by the constraints and peculiarities of the application context.

In the recent years, several works have investigated the problem of quality assessment of LD resources mainly focusing on the definition of metrics able to measure the quality of datasets according to some specific dimension [13]. In particular [14] presents an extended systemization of common potential quality issues in SKOS vocabularies and introduced automated assessment and correction tools aimed at fixing a subset of the identified quality issues. Those issues are considered from an objective point of view, disregarding any subjective evaluations that may occur according to any specific real case scenario. Therefore they are mainly devoted to reveal syntactic (i.e. with respect to the SKOS and LD specifications) or lexical issues (e.g. extra whitespace in labels). Anyway, almost all these works generally focus on sets of single quality measures, meanwhile the selection of reusable KOS may be favoured by the attribution of an overall measure able to account for the quality of thesaurus as a whole. Such an overall measure is not generally univocal, but depends from the specific application context.

This paper proposes a Multiple Attribute Decision Method (MADM) based methodology to assign a thesaurus an aggregated quality value according to the relevance of different quality measures, with respect to the requirements of the application context at hand. Considering the perspective of a TF, we dealt with two relevant application contexts relating to the framework set up and maintenance. Our contribution introduces the Thesauri Quality Assessment as the process aimed at operating a selection of SKOS thesauri based on the exploitation of an overall quality measure. The adoption of the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) [15] methodology allows capturing both subjective and objective facets involved in the TQA, and provides a ranking of the assessed thesauri. Moreover we provide a step-by-step explanation of how this approach may support the decision tasks involved in the creation and management of a TF. Our proposal is based on the thesauri and quality measures presented in [14] to which we added a further quality measure, namely the number of authoritative concepts in each thesaurus, as it provides an indirect but significant index of the quality of a thesaurus.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides the background and related work; Section 3 introduces the TQA process; Section 4 describes the MADM-based methodology in general, and AHP in particular; Section 5 illustrates an example of the application of the methodology to rank a set of thesauri according to different application contexts. Section 6 is related to the analysis of the results and Section 7 presents conclusion and future work.

2. Background and related work

If quality of information is a very long-established issue, where questions of authority, veracity and reliability raised at least since the establishment of printing in Europe, added significance has brought by recent technological developments [16]. From database system to multi-sourced and multimedia information delivered by Web 2.0 technologies, poor data quality affects many data processing tasks, such as information integration, data sharing, information retrieval, information extraction, and knowledge discovery [17].

2.1. *You cannot control what you cannot measure*

Several works [18-22] refer to Information Quality (IQ) as “fitness for use”, adopting the wider definition that Juran [23] related to those features of products or services which meet customer needs and thereby provide customer satisfaction. As noted by [19] this definition expresses a relative and task dependent concept: a satisfactory quality level for one use may be insufficient or inappropriate for another. According to [24] IQ entails two facets: i) IQ is task-dependent; ii) IQ is subjective. This definition correctly point out the importance of the awareness of recognizing the scope of an IQ process. However, it is not of a great help if it also does not specify how IQ can be obtained, given a context of use and the relative user perspective. This issue is widely examined by Naumann [25], that argues against “fitness for use” and similar visions such as the ones defining IQ as it “meets information consumers’ needs” [26], or is related to “user satisfaction” [27]. He strongly outlines that all these definitions are all as not operational as well as the Pirsing one “Even though quality cannot be defined, you know what it is” [28]. Therefore, he envisages “quality as an aggregated value of multiple IQ-criteria” and observes that this definition of IQ:

is flexible regarding the application domain, the sources, and the users, because the selection of criteria can be adapted accordingly

concluding that:

assessing scores for certain aspects of information quality and aggregating these scores are easier than immediately finding a single global IQ-score

A similar conclusion has been already asserted in [19] where the authors outlined that data quality problems can be effectively addressed only by a proper understanding of the multiple attributes or dimensions characterizing them. Various attempts to define data quality dimensions have been proposed in recent years covering different aspects of the problem such as availability, accuracy, timeliness, completeness, relevancy, consistency and so on [29-30]. In their systematization effort [18] Wang et al., after soliciting information from users regarding various data quality descriptors, resulting in over 100 items, derived about 20 categories, that they further classified into four data quality groups: intrinsic, contextual, representational, and accessibility. In another work [31] Naumann quoted the famous DeMarco's assertion [32]:

You cannot control what you cannot measure¹

and re-affirmed the importance of defining measurable quality dimensions, according to the problem at hand, for assessing the quality of a given piece of information. Furthermore, he outlined that clearly evaluating the aim of an IQ process is critical and therefore:

Why assessing IQ?

He supplied different possible answers to this question:

estimating quality relevance, significance, (“garbage in/garbage out”); need for improvement; and in case of improvement: cost-benefit ratio

According to the previous observations an IQ problem can be correctly assessed if both subjective and objective perspectives are taken into account – and if it is possible to measure them all.

2.2. SKOS quality and information quality terminology

The IQ problem has already been encountered in the LD field of which SKOS thesauri are a particular case. Various proposals arose in these last years, addressing specific aspects of linked datasets quality and proposing specific sets of metrics and methodologies for their evaluation. For instance [34] examines the ability of three classic network measures (degree, centrality, clustering coefficient) and two network measures specifically designed for LD (Open SameAs chains, and Description Richness), as one avenue of capturing the quality of interlinks amongst datasets. It leads authors to affirm that such measures are only partially effective at detecting bad links. They conclude that more tailored network measures are needed. Moreover, they recognized the need to analyse the interplay of different measures and the interpretation of the combined results. [35] introduces a quality dimension specific for the interlinking, aimed at assessing Linkset Quality for complementing third party datasets, where completeness is defined as the degree to which links in the linksets are not missing. Interlinking completeness is calculated, based on a set of scoring functions, by computing the percentage of mappable types in a dataset that have not yet been considered in the linksets when assuming an alignment among types.

Other proposals rely on the adoption of crowdsourcing techniques to assess the correctness of datasets [36, 37]. These works propose some tools generally allowing the delivery of micro-tasks (set of RDF triples possibly augmented by “surrounding” information) to more or less skilled heterogeneous crowds. After crowd judgment a re-elaboration to assess the overall dataset correctness is operated, or alternatively RDF triples judged uncorrected by the majority of the crowd participant are drop out. Often the decisions about how aggregating the crowd choices or the elimination of ‘bad’ triples (even in case of contrast judgments), are taken by adopting empirical rules. Depending on the size of the dataset exanimated, this process may be extremely time-consuming, and sometimes costly if an economic reward is owe to crowd participant, as in the case of usage of general purpose tools like for instance Amazon Mechanical Turk². Although not been specifically designed to directly operate in the context of LD, WIQA [24] is an IQ assessment framework devoted to web information consumers, which applies different filtering policies relying on complex metadata such as provenance chains and background information about providers. WIQA proposes a policy language WIQA-PL, it deploys an engine for interpreting policies and it provides explanations of why information satisfies a specific policy. However, to be effectively used it requires a considerable amount of user involvement. In [38] is

presented LUZZU a quality assessment framework for linked open data, which provides quality metadata and quality problem reports which can be used for data cleaning. LUZZU is extensible, letting third party metrics to be plugged-in the framework. Quite interestingly, authors briefly introduce a system feature enabling users to define weights on their preferred categories, dimensions or metrics that are deemed suitable for their task at hand. Based on these weights the ranking of a dataset is obtained by a weighted sum on all metrics. Not major insights are given about the underlying methodology supporting this ranking, by contrast on the well-grounded approach presented in this paper.

Particular relevant for the extension of the proposed analyses, are a recent systematic survey on quality assessment proposals for LD [13] and the deliverable produced by EU funded project PlanetData [39]. Both the works review and categorize several IQ *dimensions* which are traditionally considered in data and IQ (e.g., availability, timeliness, completeness, relevancy, availability, consistency) as well as more LD specific dimensions such as licensing and interlinking. For instance, the survey presented in [13] identifies 26 IQ dimensions, and classifies them into four major categories namely: Contextual, Intrinsic, Accessibility and Representation. An IQ *metric* is a procedure for measuring an IQ dimension. In general, more than one metric may be supplied for assessing one dimension. As quality dimensions can often be a rather abstract concept [13], metrics rely on IQ *indicators* that are characteristics of datasets (e.g., pieces of dataset content, pieces of dataset meta-information, human ratings) which can give indication about the suitability of a dataset for some intended use. The IQ *assessment* is the process of evaluating if a piece of information meets the information consumer's needs in a specific situation [24].

Our work aims at the IQ assessment of SKOS thesauri, following a bottom up approach from the identification and the assessment of single IQ dimensions to the definition of an overall IQ thesaurus assessment. This methodology computes an IQ *aggregate* thesaurus value, according to the specific context case and user's requirements. We want to notice, that as far as we observed by analysing the previous works, no explicit methodology has been proposed for what concerns the assembling of the measures resulting by applying the various proposed metrics, aimed at obtaining an overall quality evaluation of the datasets as a whole. Although we recognize that attaining such goal can be difficult or even cumbersome, we think that a reasonable and efficient way to aggregate such plethora of quality dimensions is possible. In this work we describe a methodology to assess the quality of a thesaurus as a whole based on the AHP.

When looking at the problem of the quality of thesauri, the work presented in [40] suggests a range of abstract measurement constructs based on quality notions in thesaurus literature and inference from other related literature. The declared purpose of the measurement constructs (i.e. dimensions) is to support the evaluation approaches of thesauri, but as declared by authors such constructs are solely based on theoretical analysis and they pointed out the necessity of operationalizing the measures and then refine them by application to real cases of thesauri. Moreover the presented constructs do not address quality dimensions related to multilingual thesauri. In [41] we extended [35] by proposing the linkset importing as a novel quality measure which estimates the completeness of dataset obtained by complementing SKOS thesauri with their skos:exactMatch related information. Such measure focused on easing multilingual issues such as incomplete language coverage³, an issue which affects many of the most popular SKOS thesauri. In [42] the effect of the thesaurus size on the quality of schema matching process is discussed. However, for authors self-admission measuring and assessing of the thesaurus quality is out of their research. As far as proposals facing the quality problem of SKOS thesauri, at the best of our knowledge, at present the most complete work has been provided by Suominen [14] that introduced a set of 26 quality *issues*, defined as computable functions exposing potential quality problems. By using the qSKOS tools [43] they analysed a corpus of 24 vocabularies, checking for their quality with respect to the 26 identified issues. They also applied the Skosify tool [44] to automatically correct a subset of those issues. Authors present several facets of the vocabulary quality assessment problem and supply useful observations, recommendations and best practices. Is not however their goal to address an overall measure of the quality of a vocabulary, as we propose herein. Moreover they observe, citing another work [45], that:

data quality should involve both “subjective perceptions of the individuals” and “objective measurements based on the data”

Indeed they claim their work as a contribution to the second aspects. By contrast our proposal aimed to conciliate both these polarities adopting an approach (i.e. AHP) able to consider also the subjective side of the assessment process.

3. The Thesauri Quality Assessment process

With the availability of corpora of thesauri a crucial problem occurring to thesaurus developers is evaluating and selecting thesauri which are more feasible to be reused in a new application context. Feasibility is strictly related to the concept of quality [14]. When considering SKOS thesauri several issues may hinder the quality of a thesaurus and

therefore its reuse. In previous section, we examined proposals aimed at separately evaluating the quality of various dimensions of datasets. Indeed, apart from [38], those works not address the problem of capturing the quality of a datasets as a whole. In the following, we call *Thesauri Quality Assessment* the process aimed at operating a selection of thesauri based on the exploitation of an overall quality measure.

Our aim is to present a methodology able to support the TQA based on a well-founded decision making technique, able to supply a rank for each thesaurus under evaluation. Such rank is obtained by properly aggregating several IQ dimensions. Moreover, the assessment of a set of IQ dimensions is often made under an “objective” perspective, without considering the “subjective” point of view of the expert. Dealing with subjectivity allows asserting the importance (priority) of some dimension with respect to another, or supply a judgment on dimensions that cannot quantitatively be measured (by a procedure) and required qualitatively assertion about their importance with respect to a given context. The approach we adopted is aimed at conciliating those two sides of the same coin. In this way the TQA can majorly adhere to the application context at hand, although objectively grounded on computable metrics.

3.1. The Thesauri Quality Assessment reference scenario

Our proposal relies on the work [14] which provides a thorough discussion of quality issues that hinder SKOS vocabularies and supplies a framework for the automated assessment and correction of such issues. We consider that work as a starting point to present our TQA methodology. In this way we avoided to reinvent the wheel for what concern the definition of ‘another set’ of IQ dimensions and metrics and in the meantime we were able to use the experimental outcomes therewith proposed as a benchmark to demonstrate the feasibility of our approach. In that sense we consider that work a reference scenario. We are more interested in discussing how the AHP is useful to address the TQA process and less to show the appropriateness of new IQ indicators or metrics. Furthermore, we outline that the proposed approach may be applied even if the set of indicators are different or if the assessment and correction automatic tools change.

To collect a representative data set of SKOS vocabularies, in order to ensure a wide coverage of domains, the authors of [14] looked for vocabularies in each of the seven categories of the linked open data cloud domain classification⁴. Then, for each domain, they selected one small (up to 3,000 concepts), one medium-size (3,001–10,000 concepts) and one large (more than 10,000 concepts) SKOS vocabulary. They formulated a set of 26 quality issues for SKOS vocabularies that highlighted possible problems in vocabulary quality. Such quality issues were based on earlier literature, discussions with vocabulary users, and manual analysis of vocabularies published on the web as well as existing methods for vocabulary evaluation. They also implemented checks for these issues in the qSKOS and Skosify tools. Notice that with respect to the IQ terminology reported in previous section, the term ‘issue’ (i.e. computable functions exposing potential quality problems) seems to incorporate both the dimensions (even more precisely the indicator) and the metric concept. Therefore in the following we often use them interchangeably. [14] groups issues into three categories, namely ‘Labelling and Documentation issue’, ‘Structural issues’ and ‘Linked Data issues’. In the following we consider just 20 of the 26 issues as four issues was not checked (or only partly) by the qSKOS tool, while other two belonging to the Linked Data issues category gave extremely poor values for all thesauri (i.e. approaching to 0 errors), thus we omitted them from our analysis.

In addition to the three main categories proposed in [14], the number of authoritative concepts (i.e. the concepts that are identified by URIs in the thesaurus namespace) supplied by each thesaurus, is taken as a further IQ indicator, namely ‘1.1 Authoritative Concepts’ – belonging to the category ‘1 Authoritative Concepts’ as unique element. This is not an issue itself; rather it may be regarded as a quality indicator, according to the following rule of thumb: ‘*Not Too Few/Not Too Much*’ concepts should be present in a ‘good’ thesaurus. That rule of thumb is based on a priori knowledge of thesauri available in the Web and it finds its rationale in the following considerations. Thesauri are usually deployed to index and catalogue resources. If a thesaurus has few concepts it will hardly provide the terminological coverage required to properly cover indexing for a large number of resources. On the other hand, thesauri exhibiting a huge amount of concepts are usually generated by collaborative editing or by means of automatic techniques, which may affect the overall terminological precision and coherence.

Even if not expressed in the original work, we want to point out that grouping issues in categories may facilitate the emergence of higher level views of the quality issues, allowing to highlight possible trade-offs between alternative objectives. Moreover, we numbered the four categories and the 21 quality indicators accordingly by prefixing each issue with the number of the category it belongs. This choice, although not mandatory, may visually help in applying the AHP to the problem at hand, especially in the organization of issues in a hierarchic way.

As a final observation we outline that in [14] authors explicit asserted that they:

did not assign grades of severity to the issues, because such a judgement is highly dependent on the context and intended application of the vocabulary

Our proposal is aimed at showing how, through a careful analysis of the TQA process, and through the proper adoption of the AHP, it is possible to assign issues with different priorities according to the context at hand.

3.2. Application contexts

We introduce hereafter two application contexts useful to illustrate the concepts inherent of applying the MADM based methodology as a means of capturing both the subjective and objective facets characterizing a decision problem such as TQA. These two application contexts are derived from our past experience acquired within the EU project eENVplus (<http://www.eenvplus.eu>), where we faced with the problem of reusing different thesauri for data sharing. One of the main objectives of eENVplus is the construction of a Linked TF for the environmental domain (named LusTRE) which combines existing thesauri to support metadata compilation and data discovery tasks [10].

The idea of considering frameworks of interlinked thesauri in order to make available wider terminology sources, is becoming an appealing perspective [46, 47]. The main tasks related to the life-cycle of such frameworks are: (i) the selection of existing thesauri, with emphasis on multilingualism, openness and usability features; (ii) the publication of thesauri as LD; (iii) the creation of interlinking between the published thesauri, as well as to those already made available as LD by third-parties; (iv) the management of the framework after its publication. These tasks involve at various degrees thesaurus developers and experts of the domain as well professionals in the LD sector (i.e. TF manager).

From the implementation of the TF LusTRE, we understood the importance of assessing the vocabularies quality to determine their suitability to be included in a framework. Moreover, once a TF has been built, it should be seen as a living environment, considering that possible updates to the (external) interlinked thesauri, independently operated by their owners, may change the overall quality of the framework – by possibly introducing various kinds of errors.

Based on these considerations, in the following we assume that the quality assessment of a set of thesauri occurs during two distinct application contexts AC1 and AC2, further detailed in Section 5.1:

- (1) AC1, corresponds to the thesauri selection phase aimed at identifying the suitable vocabularies to be included in a framework. The selection is carried out considering the quality issues relevant from the point of view of the thesaurus developers and domain-specific experts;
- (2) AC2, concerns the TF maintenance phase aimed at periodically evaluating the quality of the thesauri after their inclusion in the framework. It exemplifies the management task of a framework, necessary to tackle the possible errors introduced by updates which might intervene to the interlinked thesauri. The TQA, is aimed at achieving a list of thesauri majorly affected by errors, thus allowing a TF manager to firstly fix them.

4. MADM-based methodology

4.1. MADM overview

As stated above the TQA process relies on the ability to aggregating multiple quality dimensions thus to supply thesauri consumers with an overall quality measure, on the basis of which they can select the thesauri that better fit with their needs. However, due to the heterogeneity amongst multiple IQ dimensions, the task of obtaining an overall measure able to synthesize the evaluation of the various dimensions is not, in principle, an easy one.

To support the “mixing apples with oranges” process, typical of this decision task, we consider a well consolidated approach named Multi Criteria Decision Making (MCDM). According to the MCDM International Society [48]:

MCDM can be defined as the study of methods and procedures by which concerns about multiple conflicting criteria can be formally incorporated into the management planning process

MCDM methods regard the analysis of a set of various (finite or infinite) *alternatives*, namely the *decision space*, described in term of *multiple criteria*, aimed at deriving the ones that better perform respect to the goal of the planning process. In the last decades, thousands of publications have been published on MCDM methods, their development and application in different fields [49]. These methods propose procedures that, starting from the available information describing a given problem, allow evaluating the various possible alternatives (aka options) to the end of fulfil a target

objective. In order to evaluate each alternative and to compare it with others, the selection of criteria (aka attributes) is required to reflect alternative performance in meeting the objective. Criteria represent the different dimensions from which the alternatives can be viewed [50]. Each criterion must be measurable in order to assess how well a particular option is expected to perform in relation to the criterion. Criteria may be measured in cardinal numbers (e.g. price, number of drawbacks), some in binary terms (e.g. a tick indicates presence of a particular feature), or in qualitative terms (e.g. ‘good’, ‘insufficient’).

Among the several available MADM methods, the most widely adopted are: TOPSIS (Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution) [51], SAW (Simple Additive Weighting), AHP [15], and the family of methods originated by ELECTRE (ELimination and Choice Expressing REALity) [52]. [53] classifies a multi attribute decision problem as: a) Choice problem: to select a single best alternative or to reduce the group of alternative to a subset of equivalent or incomparable alternatives; b) Sorting problem: alternatives are sorted into ordered predefined categories; c) Ranking problem: alternatives are ordered in a decreasing preference list; d) Description problem: the goal is to help the description of alternatives and their consequences. This classification helps the decision makers to identify the MADM technique more suitable to address the specific formulation of a given problem.

Because of the reasons previously discussed, TQA can leverage on techniques supporting choice and/or ranking problems. As observed in [54] AHP is particularly useful for these kinds of problems. Moreover its ability of structuring a problem in a hierarchy of different levels (goal, criteria, sub-criteria and alternatives) fits well with our description of the TQA characterized by grouping the quality issues in four categories. Last but not least our choice of AHP adoption is fostered by its impressive record of successes in a number of different applications fields [55].

Figure 1. Thesauri Quality Assessment process: the role of the decision maker and the support of an AHP tool.

4.2. The Analytic Hierarchy Process

AHP supports decision-makers in structuring problem complexity and exercising judgment, allowing to incorporate both objective and subjective considerations in the decision process [56]. AHP may be operationally described by six subsequent phases: 1) identifying the criteria that characterize the alternatives of the decision problem and organizing

them as a hierarchy; 2) pairwise comparing criteria according to user preference and achieving weights derivation; 3) evaluating or gathering the performance of each alternative with respect to each criterion; 4) scaling of criteria; 5) synthesizing and ranking alternatives; 6) selecting the best alternative(s). These phases are common to all applications, in particular in Section 5 we show its adoption to the TQA process considering the two application contexts AC1 and AC2.

The overall TQA process may be depicted by the UML activity diagram of Figure 1, in which the role of the decision maker (i.e. the thesaurus developer or the TF manager) and the supporting role of an AHP tool are highlighted. We want to point out that, although in principle AHP may be applied without the use of any software, MADM tools [57] greatly simplify the decision maker activity allowing saving time and making the process more efficient. The availability of these tools allows to easily implementing the TQA process in a semi-automated way. The decision maker is involved in the choice of the criteria and their hierarchical organization as well as in their pairwise comparison that is also usually supported by the AHP software. The rest of the work is automatically executed by the software that returns the ranked list of the m alternatives (i.e. thesauri), from which the decision maker can select the one(s) fitting her needs.

4.2.1. Phase 1: Criteria selection and hierarchy creation

This phase generally starts with the selection of a set of n criteria that, according to the decision maker, qualify the decision problem at hand. A generic TQA process will base such selection on the 21 issues introduced in the reference scenario explained in Section 3.1.

Hierarchy organization helps the decision makers to organize a complex problem into its basic and simpler elements [58]. This decomposition activity sets the goal (i.e. TQA) of the analysis to the top level of the hierarchy, i.e. in our case the selection of thesauri with higher quality. Depending on the complexity of the problem, as understood by the decision maker, criteria may be further refined in sub-criteria, and so on.

4.2.2. Phase 2: Pairwise comparison of criteria and weights computation

Reciprocal paired comparisons allow expressing judgments on the relative importance of each criterion and sub-criterion and to automatically link them to a numerical fundamental scale of absolute numbers (in the integer interval 1-9) defined by Saaty [59]. This phase establishes 'local' priorities of the elements in each branch of the tree with respect to their parent node. Considering the hierarchic structure, it is made for each branch of each level, by using square matrixes with the number of element equal to the nodes at that branch. If an element X of the matrix is considered j times (with j an integer in the Saaty's scale) more important than an element Y , then it follows that Y is $1/j$ times as important as X . Based on the pairwise elicitation of relative importance of criteria given in matrix form, AHP estimate the criteria's weights. This can mainly be done using two methods: the logarithmic least squares method or the eigenvector method. The latter is advocated as more powerful dealing with inconsistencies that arise from the pairwise elicitation process [60].

Phases 1 and 2 essentially depend on the active role of the decision maker, and are fundamental to the AHP adoption as they conceive the knowledge, interest and expectation of the human expert involved in the TQA process for what concerns a specific application context. Both phases are facilitated by the use of appropriate tools allowing the decision maker to effectively insert the criteria information to be automatically elaborated in the successive phases of the process.

4.2.3. Phase 3: Performance evaluation

In a generic AHP process, the performance of each alternative, is function of the performance of n criteria which values may derived by observation of exogenous factors (e.g. an observation of a natural phenomenon, the cost or monetary value of a good or service), may be obtained by some procedural algorithm or formula or may be established by subjective perspective (either qualitative or quantitative) of the decision maker that may assert the priority of an attribute for a certain alternative based on her knowledge of the problem context.

Considering the TQA process, we assumed that the quality performance value of each criterion (except for the newly introduced '1.1 Authoritative Concepts' criterion) may be computed by using an open source tool such as qSKOS, aimed at highlighting vocabularies quality issues. However, we gather the values from the application of qSKOS to the 24 thesauri of the reference scenario. For each criterion C_i the associated performance value P_i is supplied by the number of errors computed for a given thesaurus.

4.2.4. Phase 4: Scaling criteria

Prior to compare the m alternatives, the original performance values of every criterion measured according to different scales, have to be transformed in relative values called *scores*. As performance values can be supplied in numeric,

descriptive or categorical data, the scaling of criteria solves the problems of different ranges and different units of the performance values. As noted by [25] the goal of scaling is to bring all criterion values into non-dimensional scores within the [0, 1] interval, and thus make them comparable. To achieve this *normalization* task Saaty proposed different methods [61]. In particular the so-called *Ideal* mode compares each performance value P_i to a fixed benchmark, such as for example the performance value of the best alternative under criterion C_i . In its general application the *Ideal* mode computes the score values $S(C_i)$ by dividing P_i by the maximum value achieved for criterion C_i amongst all the alternatives.

Figure 2. Generic tree with root labelled ‘Goal’.

4.2.5. Phase 5: Synthesis and ranking

Once scores have been computed for each criterion of each alternative, they are combined with the criteria weights derived from pairwise comparisons (phase 2) to determine an overall synthesis score for each alternative. This value is obtained by adding the products of each criterion score $S(C_i)$ with its associated weight w_i , across each branch of the hierarchy. This sum is the score value for the parent node directly above and the process is repeated at the next level of the hierarchy until the root node is reached. Let us consider, for example, objective O_2 with three sub-criteria in the generic tree T rooted with the ‘Goal’ node in Figure 2. After pairwise comparison the weight for each criterion C_{21} , C_{22} and C_{23} has been determined to be w_{21} , w_{22} and w_{23} respectively. The scaling phase has been assigned to each of these criteria a normalized value: $S(C_{21})$, $S(C_{22})$ and $S(C_{23})$. The overall score for the objective O_2 , i.e. $S(O_2)$, is given by the sum of the products of each criterion score by its associated weight, yielding the value:

$$S(O_2) = S(C_{21}) * w_{21} + S(C_{22}) * w_{22} + S(C_{23}) * w_{23} \tag{1}$$

Assuming that the scoring for objective O_1 has been similarly computed, giving a value $S(O_1)$, the overall synthesized score $S(T)$ for the tree T of Figure 2 is given by:

$$S(T) = S(\text{Goal}) = S(O_1) * w_1 + S(O_2) * w_2 \tag{2}$$

This task is applied to all the alternatives under exam. Based on the synthesized scores an overall ranking is obtained by sorting the alternatives. These ranks account for the level of fulfilment of each alternative in achieving the goal.

4.2.6. Phase 6: Selection

The last AHP phase is the choice of the best alternative or the selection amongst the best ranking ones. It is left to the decision maker, when the ranking list of the alternatives is returned.

5. TQA in a real setting

We investigate the feasibility of applying AHP to TQA process in a real setting highlighting the importance of assigning diverse relevancies to the IQ issues according to the application context. In the following, the phases of the AHP process

are illustrated in order to provide a practical example of how to apply the methodology. Let us note that the validation of the MADM methodology, and particularly of AHP, is clearly out of the scope of this paper. In fact, notwithstanding there are plenty of real case scenarios in which AHP has been already successfully adopted, some criticism arose in the years, that was countered by arguments of Saaty himself and other methodology proponents [62].

The real setting considers two perspectives: the TF creation and TF management. The input data are the set of vocabularies and the quality measures provided by the reference scenario and the two application contexts AC1 and AC2. The performance values listed in tables 6, 7 and 8 of [14] are used, and different priorities are supplied to criteria according to the specific peculiarities of each context. The choice of using the 24 heterogeneous thesauri in [14] has been convenient as it spared us the burden of selecting specific thesauri belonging to a specific application domain and apply the qSKOS tool on it⁵, which is obviously the ‘canonical’ situation occurring when building or maintaining a TF. More important, the values presented in [14], may be used as a benchmark for applying alternative methodologies and comparing them with the one presented in this paper. Although this may be seen as a stretch from the reality, we think that this approach does not affect the outcomes of our testing aimed at providing a proof of concept of the our methodology on real numbers.

Table 1. Thesauri quality issues grouped by category and assignment of priorities to criteria by the decision maker with respect to the two application context AC1, AC2: R (Relevant), L (Less Relevant), I (Irrelevant).

Quality Issues Category	Quality issue	AC1	AC2
1 Authoritative Concepts		R	I
	1.1 Authoritative Concepts	R	I
2 Labelling and Documentation issues		R	R
	2.1 Omitted invalid tags (*)	I	R
	2.2 Incomplete Language Coverage	R	I
	2.3 Undocumented concept	L	I
	2.4 Overlapping labels	R	I
	2.5 Inconsistent prefLabel (*)	I	R
	2.6 Disjoint Label Violation (*)	I	R
	2.7 Extra whitespace in labels	I	R
3 Structural issues		R	R
	3.1 Orphan concepts	R	I
	3.2 Disconnected concept cluster	R	I
	3.3 Cyclic hierarchical relations (*)	I	R
	3.4 Valueless Associative relations	L	I
	3.5 Solely transitively concept (*)	I	R
	3.6 Omitted Top Concept	L	L
	3.7 Top concept Having Broader concept	I	R
	3.8 Unidirectionally related concept (*)	I	R
	3.9 Relational Clashes (*)	I	R
	3.10 Mapping clashes	R	R
4 Linked Data issues		L	R
	4.1 Missing Inlinks	I	R
	4.2 Missing Out Links	L	R
	4.3 Broken links	R	R

* Issue fixable by applying the Skosify tool.

5.1. Context setting

Table 1 reports the 21 quality issues grouped in the four categories along with the assignment of priorities to criteria by the two decision makers, i.e. thesaurus developer and TF manager, respectively involved into AC1 and AC2 and are driven by our experience in the deployment of LusTRE framework.

We assumed that the evaluation of the relevance of each criteria and category is given by assigning one of three possible values: R (Relevant), L (Less Relevant), I (Irrelevant). Irrelevant criteria are those that are not included in the hierarchy for that context. Notice that the choice of these three values is absolutely subjective according with the point of view of the decision maker respect to the role that each quality issue plays in the two contexts.

As regards context AC1, the quality assessment aims at assessing the appropriateness of including a thesaurus in the TF. The assignment of priorities is the following: (i) the ‘1 Authoritative Concepts’ category is considered relevant as it semantically represents the importance of a thesaurus in terms of the number and the correctness of its concepts according to the “Not Too Few/Not Too Much” rule of thumb; (ii) those quality issues that can be fixed automatically by the Skosify tool (indicated with an asterisk in Table 1) or by applying a simple trimming procedure as for ‘2.7 Extra whitespace in labels’, are irrelevant. The rationale behind this choice is that such issues do not affect the overall quality computed by AHP as an automatic procedure to fix a quality issue exists; (iii) issues such as ‘2.2 Incomplete Language Coverage’, ‘2.4 Overlapping Labels’ and ‘3.1 Orphan concepts’, are considered particularly relevant for the effective reusability of the thesaurus by the end user, while the importance of other issues such as ‘3.4 Valueless associative relations’ and ‘3.6 Omitted top concept’, is relaxed according to the needs of the decision maker. For instance ‘3.4 Valueless associative relations’ may be judged less relevant because skos:related are sometimes specialized with other properties, hence the fact that two siblings have an association might not necessary imply a bad modelling; (iv) ‘4 Linked Data’ category has a lower relevance than the other three categories, as AC1 focuses on the selection of thesauri to be inserted in the framework.

As regards context AC2, TQA is devoted to the TF management phase concerning the identification of thesauri (and their interlinking) deployed within the TF which may require fine-tuning with automatic procedures. The assignment of priorities is the following: (i) ‘1 Authoritative Concepts’ category is not considered, because all the evaluated thesauri in AC2 are assumed to be already included in the TF; (ii) the three other categories are significant: in particular quality issues that can be fixed automatically by the Skosify tool (marked with an asterisk) are all relevant while issues that intrinsically qualify the content of a thesaurus (such as ‘2.2 Incomplete Language Coverage’, ‘2.3 Undocumented concept’ and ‘2.4 Overlapping labels’) are not considered at all in the TF management phase, as they consist of editorial changes of which a framework manager is not usually in charge; (iii) all the quality issues in the ‘4 Linked Data’ category are relevant as the TF management imply the improvement of the interlinking between vocabularies in the TF and with other thesauri available as LD.

5.2. Applying AHP

In the following we show how to apply the AHP phases introduced in Section 4.2 to the AC1 and AC2 contexts. Several AHP tools are available [57], some of them requiring a fee, while others allow free usage or trials. In the following we used SuperDecisions⁶ as it granted us a free trial for a period of one year.

5.2.1. AHP Phase 1

With respect to the generic TQA scenario discussed in Section 4.2.1 only the criteria relevant for each specific application context are selected. Figure 3 and Figure 4 illustrate the trees for the two contexts, according to the priorities of quality criteria as reported in Table 1. If an issue is not relevant for the application context, there is not a corresponding node in the tree. The two trees are rooted with ‘TQA’ as the goal of the decision process.

5.2.2. AHP Phase 2

Table 2 shows the pairwise comparison for the second level of AC1 tree (Figure 3). The pairwise assessment of the four categories is given by the 4 x 4 matrix, where has been assumed that ‘1 Authoritative Concepts’, ‘2 Labelling and Documentation’ and ‘3 Structural’ categories are, in this case, twice more important than ‘4 Linked data’ (see Table 1).

Figure 3. Applying the phase I of AHP to the application context AC1.

Figure 4. Applying the phase I of AHP to the application context AC2.

Table 2. Pairwise assessment of the four quality categories under the TQA goal with respect context AC1.

	1 Authoritative Concepts	2 Labelling and Documentation	3 Structural	4 LinkedData
1 Authoritative Concepts	1	1	1	2
2 Labelling and Documentation	1	1	1	2
3 Structural	1	1	1	2
4 Linked Data	1/2	1/2	1/2	1

The same process is repeated for all the branches of all levels. Thus for AC1 we must complete a 3x3 matrix, a 5 x 5 and a 2 x 2 matrix for the criteria at the leaves level. For instance Figure 5 shows the elicitation of criteria priorities for the category ‘3 Structural’ in AC1 context with the use of SuperDecisions. According to the priorities, as presented in Table 1, SuperDecisions allows establishing the pairwise priorities amongst the five criteria belonging to the structural issue category. The tool provides the insertion of priority in matrix form, however, as the inverse values are directly computed, just the triangular matrix has to be filled. Moreover the priority of last criterion (i.e. ‘3.10 Mapping clashes’) compared to the others is not explicitly given, as it can be computed by the values supplied in the other cells. The weights are automatically computed by SuperDecisions according to the mathematics presented in [63].

The same process has been applied to AC2.

Figure 5. Pairwise comparison and computation of relative weights given in (triangular) matrix form for the Structural issue category according to the AC1 context. To the right are the normalized weights computed by the tool.

5.2.3. AHP Phase 3

The third AHP phase requires the computation of performance values of each criterion C_i according to every thesaurus. With respect to [14] we have only to assign values to ‘1 Authoritative Concepts’, as for the other 20 criteria we borrowed the performance values (i.e. number of computed errors) presented in [14]. To this end we mapped values to the absolute number of authoritative concepts of each thesaurus according to the “Not Too Few/Not Too Much” principle. These values have been assigned after having conveniently categorized the number of authoritative concepts based on the knowledge of the thesaurus expert.

One of the main assumption of many MADM method, and primarily of AHP, is that in many real-life situations not all criteria can be objectively measured, but a decision scenario is often greatly affected by the decision maker point of view, based on his/her experience, expectation, evaluation. MADM methods allow to cope with such kind of subjectivity (also referred as *intangibility*), and to transform it in something measureable for which an overall decision process between alternatives can be carried out. We leveraged on the capability of the SuperDecisions tool to translate the expert knowledge in modelling the “Not Too Few/Not Too Much” rule of thumb. To this end a category of five qualitative values has been set up: “Very Good”, “Good”, “Medium”, “Sufficient” and “Unsatisfactory”. For instance

DBpedia has been set as “Unsatisfactory”, since it provides more than 800,000 authoritative concepts, which resulting from a crowd-sourced community effort, present a quite variable level of accuracy. By contrast, AGROVOC has been set “Very Good” since it provides a good number of authoritative concepts (more than 30,000) published and maintained by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations and its community of experts. EARTH is set as “Good” as it provides less authoritative concepts as AGROVOC but it is still maintained by a community of experts. GEMET is set as “Medium” since it provides less authoritative concepts than EARTH but with a good level of accuracy. The SuperDecisions tool supplies an easily interface to create such set of nominal categories, and to compare their relevance through the same pair-wise approach supporting the criteria comparison (see Figure 6). Based on the user choices the tool assigns a numeric value to each qualitative value that, in the specific case, are respectively 1, 0.62, 0.369, 0.211, 0.106 (rounded at the third digit, and normalized with respect the higher value).

Figure 6. Assigning priorities to the five qualitative values accounting for the relevance of each thesaurus according to the number of authoritative concepts.

5.2.4. AHP phase 4

Before applying the fourth phase of the AHP methodology, i.e. the evaluation of the scores $S(C_i)$ for each criterion C_i of each thesaurus T_i ($i=1, \dots, 24$), we must operate a pre-processing step to make the actual performance quality values be ingested by a AHP tool. This pre-processing is usually not necessary in decision scenarios that adopt AHP to compare alternatives such as, for instance when evaluating the price of goods, the air pollution caused by alternative producing plants, the horse power and energy consumption of vehicles and so on. However in our case the performance values are supplied, by qSKOS, as absolute number of errors for any given IQ issue and thesaurus, while the assessed thesauri have different size (i.e. different number of authoritative concepts). Thus prior to be normalized such performance values have to be measured on a comparable scale or in other word their absolute values have to be relativized to the thesaurus size.

We therefore replaced the absolute performance value for a criterion C_i given an alternative T_i , with the ratio:

$$P_{ij} = \frac{\#error_{ij}}{\#authconcept(T_i)} \quad (3)$$

Once all ratios are computed for each criterion and alternative, the usual AHP scaling phase may be applied. Considering that the best result is when $P_{ij} = 0$ (i.e. no errors), we cannot use directly the *Ideal* approach, mentioned in Section 4.2.4, that normalizes the values for a given criterion by dividing for the maximum (assuming this is the best one). We therefore applied the following normalization formula to compute the score value S_{ij} :

$$S_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{P_{ij}}{\max_j}, & \max_j \neq 0 \\ 1, & \max_j = 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where \max_j is the maximum (relative) error measured for a given criterion C_i (i.e. $\max_j = \max\{P_{ij}, i=1, \dots, 24\}$). Thus, as expected, the lesser the error the greater the score achieved by a thesaurus for a given criterion, that will contribute to increase the ranking of the thesaurus when coupled with the computed weights. If for a criterion C_k , no error is reported for every thesaurus T_i , then $S_{ik} = 1$ for all i . The scores have been computed based on the absolute performance values contained in Table 6, 7 and 8 of [14] and are reported in Table 3 in Appendices.

5.2.5. AHP Phase 5

Based on the overall synthesis score achieved by each thesaurus, according to the process explained in Section 4.2.5, SuperDecisions computes and returns a ranking list of the 24 alternative thesauri. The ranking of thesauri according to the two contexts AC1 and AC2 are reported in Figure 7 and discussed in the next section.

6. Discussion

The AHP process has been applied to either the contexts AC1 and AC2 achieving the ranking of thesauri reported by the graphs of Figure 7, where ranking values are normalized with respect to the first ranked thesaurus.

At first look the graphs immediately reveals how the ranking consistently changed according to the application context peculiarities. These results witness the ability of AHP in the provision of an overall quality measure for each alternative thesaurus, with respect to different context scenarios, thus confirming to be a feasible means in supporting the TQA selection process. Therefore considering that as pointed out by Saaty:

Comparison requires the use of judgment. Even informed judgment is subjective

we delineate our analysis to examine the consistency of TQA outcomes with respect to the context-driven choices made by an informed decision maker (i.e. thesaurus developer and TF manager) and to the performance values obtained by each thesaurus, after having been normalized (see Table 3). Some consideration can be drawn from the analysis of the thesauri rankings obtained with respect to the two contexts.

Let us consider the first and second thesauri ranking in AC1: UMBEL and AGROVOC. These thesauri ranked 17th and 13th respectively when considered in the other scenario AC2. Such results are largely explained by the presence in AC1 of the '1.1 Authoritative concepts' criterion for which both UMBEL and AGROVOC have been assigned the higher value 'Very Good' (i.e. 1). This accounts on the total value computed by AHP, for a contribution of $0.2857=1*0.2857$ for both thesauri (hereafter we marked in italic the weights computed by the SuperDecisions tool). Obviously, such a good performance value is entirely lost when considering AC2 where '1.1 Authoritative concepts' is irrelevant.

As a general example of application of the synthesis phase of AHP to a real setting, let us consider how UMBEL ranked best than AGROVOC (according to AC1). To this end we compute the singular performance scores achieved by the two thesauri for the other three categories. As for '2 Labelling and Documentation' category, UMBEL scored $0.264=(1*0.4+0.892*0.2+0.868*0.4)*0.2857$ versus $0.195=(0.731*0.4+0.077*0.2+0.945*0.4)*0.2857$ of AGROVOC. As for '3 Structural' UMBEL scores $0.276=(0.889*0.25+0.973*0.25+1*0.125+1*0.125+1*0.25)*0.2857$ slightly outperformed by AGROVOC scoring $0.281=(1*0.25+0.94*0.25+0.994*0.125+1*0.125+1*0.25)*0.2857$. Finally for '4 Linked Data' category, with a weight of 0.1429 according to the judgment on priorities as shown in Table 1, UMBEL outperforms AGROVOC achieving a partial score of $0.1429=(1*0.3333+1*0.6667)*0.1429$ against $0.1174=(0.465*0.3333+1*0.6667)*0.1429$. The overall score for the TQA process of the two thesauri are therefore 0.9686 and 0.8791, that normalized with respect to UMBEL give the values depicted in Figure 7.

From a thesaurus developer point of view, these partial scores highlight that UMBEL is significantly better than AGROVOC when considering the labelling and documentation issues and the linked data issues, and very close to AGROVOC when looking at the structure issues. Without repeating the same process for other thesauri, we observe that following the first two thesauri in the AC1 ranking, come EARTH and LVAK evaluated with 'Good' performance (0.62 score) for '1 Authoritative concepts', both achieving a partial score of $0.177=0.62*0.2857$ but downgrading to 8th and 16th in AC2.

Figure 7. Ranking of the 24 thesauri according to context AC1 (left) and AC2 (right).

By contrast, if we look at the four thesauri achieving an ‘Unsatisfactory’ judgment for the first category, we notice that only GeoNames is effectively penalized by this lower score, achieving a partial score of $0.03=(0.106*0.2857)$. Indeed GeoNames ranks 5th in AC2 context. The other three ‘Unsatisfactory’ thesauri, ODT, Reagle and DBpedia almost achieve very similar ranks when evaluated according to AC2, thus indicating their bad performance also for the other three categories.

One interesting consideration rises when looking at the substantial difference of the ranking of the first four thesauri in AC1 and in AC2. As noted these are largely explained by the presence of the ‘1.1 Authoritative concepts’ criteria. However, it is important to outline that the other components affecting the scores of each category up to the goal are the weights. AHP computes these values based on the expert’s pairwise judgments on criteria at the various level of the hierarchy. In the case of AC1, the choice of assigning equal importance to the first three categories, and judging them more important than the fourth (i.e. ‘4 Linked Data’), implies a strong relevance assigned to ‘1.1 Authoritative concepts’. It is up to the decision maker to evaluate if that choice is sound with respect the intended meaning of the TQA process considering the application context under exam. Obviously the same observation is generally valid for all the categories and all the criteria.

The previous consideration raises an important issue concerning the MADM adoption, and relates to the common practice in MADM applications to adjust or revise the set of criteria, or their relative importance. This often leads to a feedback process, namely sensitive analysis [65] that can support decision makers to test how different settings could influence the TQA results. Such analysis is useful, and sometimes essential both in cases of doubts about the ‘winning’ alternative(s), or to study the impact of different weights, due for instance to the discovery of a new relevant criterion or to changes at the fitness of the usage scenario (i.e. different expectations on the set of criteria). For this reason it may be considered an important aspect when applying MADM techniques in real life problem. We invite the interested reader to consult the above-cited work, or Masuda [66] which focuses on some sensitivity issues of the AHP process.

Without repeating the previous detailed analysis, from the comparison of the values of the two histograms Figure 7 and clearly appears that in AC2 thesauri ranking values are closer than in AC1. As explained, this fact is largely due to the presence in AC1 of ‘1.1 Authoritative concepts’, that substantially increases the values of the first two thesauri, while the remaining 22 range in a (normalized) interval of [0.5, 0.8]. Approximately this is the same size range (i.e. 0.3) into which all 24 thesauri ranked in AC2 (i.e. in the [0.7, 1] interval). Moreover in AC2 the first three thesauri are very close to each other, with very marginal differences. They are followed by DDC, Plant and GeoNames all with a ranking value greater than 0.9. There are then twelve thesauri ranking in the interval [0.8, 0.9]. The last six thesauri rank in [0.8, 0.9].

Finally, we remind that in AC2 the overall quality assessment is devoted to identify thesauri for which some adjustment can be done with automatic procedures. This is the reason of having included all seven ‘fixable’ criteria. As a rationale the resulting ranking of AC2 has to be used by a TF manager in the inverse order: thesauri with lower ranks required to be fixed before better ranking ones.

7. Conclusions

In this paper we propose the adoption of the AHP as a means to assess the quality of SKOS thesauri. Differently by other proposals, that define metrics measuring distinct pieces of linked datasets, we focus on providing an overall quality measure able to synthesize a heterogeneous set of quality dimensions. We discuss the role of the AHP in capturing both subjective and objective facets involved in the selection of thesauri, and its ability in providing a ranking of the assessed thesauri. Moreover, as a guideline to replicate our approach, we provided a step-by-step explanation of how AHP supports the decision tasks involved in two real application contexts: the creation and the management of a linked TF.

Future research may extend the use of MADM-AHP methodology to the quality assessment of other kinds of (i.e. non thesauri) datasets available in the linked open data cloud that is becoming a relevant topic in the semantic web world⁷. The future research would define an aggregating measure, based on the several quality dimensions presented in works like [13], and possibly integrating other metrics and dimensions should appear in future works.

Notes

1. It is worth noting that 1982 De Marco's work, addressed the Software Engineering (SE) process, and since then it was, more or less, appropriately quoted in thousands of works, even not specific to the SE sector. More recently he returned on his statement [33] and although he reaffirmed that "this line contains a real truth," it also argued about its absolute efficacy in the SE sector, asserting that "software development is inherently different from a natural science such as physics, and its metrics are accordingly much less precise in capturing the things they set out to describe." We agree, however, with [31] upon the significance of DeMarco's early quotation, when related to IQ and on the importance to define clear and measurable dimensions for IQ. In the present paper we aim at demonstrating that notwithstanding IQ cannot certainly be considered a natural science, and several IQ dimensions are subjective and sometimes difficult to measure, the effort to precisely defining them worth the price.
2. <http://aws.amazon.com/mturk/>
3. Incomplete language coverage arises when `skos:prefLabel` and `skos:altLabel` are provided in all the expected languages only for a subset of the thesaurus concepts.
4. <http://wifo5-03.informatik.uni-mannheim.de/lodcloud/state/#domains>
5. Indeed some preliminary work is required, according to authors declaring that prior to apply the qSKOS tool they "converted the vocabularies into a uniform format, manually correcting syntactic or representation related issues when necessary" [14]
6. <http://www.superdecisions.com/>
7. <http://ldq.semanticmultimedia.org/>

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Appendices

Table 3 Normalized performance values of quality criteria – (IA.C. stands for ‘I Authoritative concepts)

	1 A. C.	2 Labelling and Documentation							3 Structural							4 Linked Data						
	1.1 Authoritative concepts	2.1 Omitted invalid tags (*)	2.2 Incomplete Language Coverage	2.3 Undocumented concept	2.4 Overlapping labels	2.5 Inconsistent prefLabel (*)	2.6 Disjoint Label Violation (*)	2.7 Extra whitespace in labels	3.1 Orphan concepts	3.2 Disconnected concept cluster	3.3 Cyclic hierarchical relations (*)	3.4 Valueless Associative relations	3.5 Solely transitively concept(*)	3.6 Omitted Top Concept (*)	3.7 Top concept Having Broader concept	3.8 Unidirectionally related concept (*)	3.9 Relational Clashes (*)	3.10 Mapping clashes	4.1 Missing Inlinks	4.2 Missing Out Links	4.3 Broken links	
ODT	0.106	0.972	0.959	0.673	0.987	1.000	0.941	1.000	0.963	0.456	1.000	0.953	1.000	1.000	0.000	0.569	1.000	1.000	0.000	0.710	0.981	
Eurovoc	0.369	0.968	0.746	0.214	0.994	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.999	0.995	1.000	0.999	1.000	0.989	1.000	0.230	1.000	1.000	0.125	0.000	0.000	
UMBEL	1.000	0.023	1.000	0.892	0.868	0.998	1.000	0.967	0.889	0.973	0.855	1.000	0.000	1.000	1.000	0.990	1.000	1.000	0.046	1.000	1.000	
GeoNames	0.106	1.000	0.983	0.912	0.840	0.953	1.000	1.000	0.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.966	0.000	0.999	
NYTL	0.211	1.000	1.000	0.030	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.961	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.050	1.000	0.960	
EARTH	0.620	0.999	0.994	0.454	0.902	1.000	0.970	0.964	0.841	0.795	1.000	0.944	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.691	0.981	1.000	0.036	0.334	0.998	
Reegle	0.106	0.998	0.728	0.998	0.990	1.000	0.987	0.941	0.997	0.989	1.000	0.000	0.580	1.000	1.000	0.565	0.000	0.000	0.036	0.441	0.988	
IPSV	0.369	1.000	1.000	0.038	1.000	1.000	0.972	1.000	1.000	0.998	1.000	0.962	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.998	0.995	1.000	0.036	0.000	1.000	
LVAk	0.620	0.000	1.000	0.000	0.999	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.998	0.993	0.715	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.554	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.000	1.000	
PXV	0.211	0.064	1.000	0.115	0.997	1.000	0.985	0.998	0.999	0.951	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.968	0.408	0.995	1.000	0.036	0.380	0.996	
GEMET	0.369	0.999	0.953	1.000	0.532	1.000	0.996	0.996	1.000	0.992	1.000	0.996	1.000	0.985	1.000	0.321	0.998	1.000	0.391	0.888	1.000	
SNOMED	0.369	0.000	1.000	0.000	0.999	1.000	0.988	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.999	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.784	0.945	1.000	0.036	1.000	1.000	
IPTC	0.211	1.000	1.000	0.547	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.960	1.000	1.000	0.610	1.000	1.000	0.602	1.000	1.000	0.036	0.547	1.000	
NYTP	0.369	1.000	1.000	0.178	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.998	0.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.985	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.039	1.000	1.000	
GTAA	0.369	1.000	1.000	0.437	0.954	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.058	0.970	1.000	0.961	1.000	0.996	1.000	0.960	0.999	1.000	0.036	0.000	1.000	
UNESCO	0.211	1.000	1.000	0.000	0.939	1.000	1.000	0.000	1.000	0.997	1.000	0.995	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.982	1.000	1.000	0.036	0.000	1.000	
STW	0.369	0.993	0.000	0.221	0.000	0.000	1.000	1.000	0.990	0.827	1.000	0.470	1.000	0.978	1.000	0.000	0.997	1.000	0.037	0.785	0.996	
LCSH	0.211	0.755	1.000	0.245	0.987	0.948	0.997	1.000	0.577	0.546	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.914	1.000	1.000	0.036	0.150	1.000	
AGROVOC	1.000	1.000	0.731	0.077	0.945	1.000	0.529	0.890	1.000	0.940	1.000	0.994	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.765	1.000	1.000	0.054	0.465	1.000	
RAMEAU	0.211	0.439	0.816	0.661	0.982	1.000	0.000	0.937	0.584	0.000	0.985	0.982	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.431	0.992	1.000	0.036	0.832	0.964	
DDC	0.211	1.000	0.830	0.000	0.892	1.000	1.000	0.997	0.614	0.931	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.991	0.615	0.993	1.000	1.000	0.041	0.998	1.000	
SSW	0.211	0.998	0.841	0.317	0.987	1.000	0.948	0.995	0.997	0.996	1.000	0.956	0.992	1.000	1.000	0.864	0.991	1.000	0.037	0.173	0.992	
Plant	0.211	1.000	1.000	0.932	0.989	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.944	1.000	0.233	1.000	1.000	0.275	0.634	1.000	1.000	0.036	1.000	0.989	
DBpedia	0.106	1.000	1.000	0.000	0.999	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.880	0.989	0.000	0.993	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.275	0.946	1.000	0.036	0.000	0.999	

* Issue fixable by applying the Skosify tool.